
WPs-2250-2251 CCN10: “DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site”

[D-3]
**Study of HCHO/NO₂ ratio versus Ozone at ground at
San Pietro Capofiume using SkySpec-2D MAX-DOAS
measurements**

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AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
1.0	30/08/2024	Creation of D-3 “Study of HCHO/NO ₂ ratio versus Ozone at ground at San Pietro Capofiume using SkySpec-2D MAX-DOAS measurements” document of project “WPs-2250-2251: DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site” CCN10

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1. List of Acronyms

ARPAE	Agenzia regionale per la prevenzione, l'ambiente e l'energia dell'Emilia-Romagna
CCN	Contract Change Notice
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
HYSPLIT	Hybrid Single-Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory
ISAC	Istituto di Scienze dell'Atmosfera e del Clima
MAX-DOAS	Multi AXis – DOAS
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
QA4EO	Quality Assurance For Earth Observation
SPC	San Pietro Capofiume
UTC	Universal Time Coordinate
VCDs	Vertical Column Densities
VOCs	Volatile Organic Compounds

2. Introduction

This document is the report of the activities performed in the frame of WPs 2250-1.1, 1.2, 1.3 of the IDEAS-QA4EO WPs-2250-2251 “DOAS-BO: Towards a new FRM4DOAS-compliant site” CCN10. The WP 2250-1 is centered on the processing of MAX-DOAS SkySpec-2D measurements at San Pietro Capofiume (therein SPC) “Giorgio Fea” ISAC-CNR observatory in the Po Valley for the retrieval of HCHO (formaldehyde) tropospheric profiles. The main outcomes of these WPs have been reported in D-2A “San Pietro Capofiume HCHO tropospheric profiles and VCDs dataset from SkySpec-2D MAX-DOAS measurements and comparisons with TROPOMI Tropospheric VCDs”.

At the same time, several papers (e.g., [RD-1]) demonstrated the capability of satellite and MAX-DOAS ground-based measurements to discuss the VOC/NO_x regime in relations to O₃ formation in pollution conditions. The use of the HCHO/NO₂ ratio, as suggested in [RD-2] for satellite data, is an indicator for the ozone production regime. VOC sensitive (or limited) regimes are represented by HCHO/NO₂ ratio less than 1 while values greater than 2 indicate a NO_x sensitive (or limited) regime. In the intermediate regime, there is a sensitivity towards both NO_x and VOCs. In this report, we describe the ratio of HCHO and NO₂ tropospheric VCDs calculated from SPC data from October 2021 to December 2022 in relation with O₃ data at ground from ARPAE measurements to investigate the VOCs/NO_x -limited regime at SPC.

3. Ozone, wind, temperature and relative humidity measurements at SPC

ARPAE routinely measures O₃ at SPC and the products are freely available at the ARPAE website (<https://dati.arpae.it/dataset/qualita-dell-aria-rete-di-monitoraggio/resource/7efd47bc-31e3-4f7d-bca4-e1b01f80a304>). We selected the SPC station (station id: 7.000.027) and downloaded the hourly averaged ozone data provided as concentration (µg/m³). For our scope, we produced daily averages of these data considering the time frame between 10:00 and 18:00. This time frame was selected in order to be in good temporal collocation with MAX-DOAS data coverage (that is linked to the daylight). We compared also these averages with the 8 hours means provided by ARPAE and we checked that the difference is minimum. In this report, we adopted 120 µg/m³ as maximum limit for the daily 8-hours mean (D. Lgs. 155/2010). This threshold is one of the standards set and monitored by the European Ambient Air Quality Directives (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/air/air-quality_en) to reduce air pollution by ozone and its impacts on health. Considering that the exposure to high concentrations of ground-level ozone can cause and aggravate cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, the authorities in the affected areas and countries have to take specific measures.

In addition to ozone data provided by ARPAE, we used wind, temperature and relative humidity at ground (12 m a.s.l) as extracted from SPC radio soundings at 12:00 UTC (<https://weather.uwyo.edu/upperair/sounding.html>). Those data were used as correlative information and cover the whole 2022.

4. HCHO/NO₂ ratio using retrievals from SkySpec-2D MAX-DOAS measurements

For the computation of the HCHO/NO₂ ratio, we used HCHO and NO₂ daily averages. The main results that we obtained are reported in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: HCHO and NO₂ timeseries (Top panel); HCHO/NO₂ ratio and O₃ at surface (middle panel) and Temperature, wind speed and RH (bottom panel). See text for details.

In the top panel of Fig. 1, we reported the daily averages of HCHO (in black) and NO₂ (in red) tropospheric columns. The vertical bars are the standard deviations of the daily means. The ratio

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HCHO/NO₂ is reported into the middle panel of Fig. 1 with black dots. As can be noticed, the ratio is lower in winter and higher in summer, where the value of the ratio exceeds 2 (dashed black horizontal line), with a peak in August 2022. In the same panel, we reported the daily averages of the O₃ concentrations (computed starting from ARPAE hourly observations) as a solid blue line. The horizontal blue dotted line marks the 120 µg /m³ limit for O₃. In the lowest panel, we reported temperature (°C, black dots), relative humidity (% , blue dots) and wind intensity (knots, red crosses) at the surface measured by radio soundings.

In Fig. 2, we reported the scatter plot of the HCHO/NO₂ ratio versus O₃ at the surface. The correlation (R²) of HCHO/NO₂ ratio and O₃ is 0.78. We observed that most of the O₃ values that exceed the 120 µg /m³ limit are associated to ratio higher than 2.

In Fig. 3, we reported the scatter plots of temperature (left panel) and relative humidity (right panel) versus O₃ daily mean concentrations at the surface. O₃ is strongly (R²=0.85) correlated with temperature and anticorrelated (R²=-0.79) with RH.

San Pietro Capofiume - HCHO/NO₂ daily Tropospheric VCDs vs O₃ at surface

Figure 2: Scatter plot of O₃ versus the HCHO/NO₂ ratio. The vertical line marks the 120 µg/m³ limit for O₃. The two horizontal lines mark the ratio of 1 and 2.

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Figure 3: Left panel: Scatter plot of O_3 versus temperature. Right panel: Scatter plot of O_3 versus RH. The vertical line marks the $120 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Figure 4: Left panel: Scatter plot of HCHO/NO₂ versus temperature. Right panel: Scatter plot of HCHO/NO₂ versus relative humidity. The horizontal line marks the ratio at 1 and 2.

In Fig. 4, we show the scatter plots of temperature (left panel) and relative humidity (right panel) versus the HCHO/NO₂ ratio. Also in this case, the ratio is strongly correlated ($R^2 = 0.87$) with temperature while the anticorrelation with relative humidity is lower ($R^2 = -0.5$) than the one observed against O_3 .

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Figure 5: Same as in Fig. 1 but with ΔO_3 .

As discussed in [RD-3], it is not possible to know the rate of O_3 production. O_3 values measured during the day can be the result of both transport processes and in-situ photochemical ozone production. In order to remove the transport effects as much as possible, we used instead of the daily O_3 averages only, the differences between the daily O_3 averages (08:00-18:00 UTC) and the night averages (00:00-04:00). This quantity is named ΔO_3 value and is plotted in Fig. 5 in the second panel.

5. Discussions

Fig. 1 highlighted how much the behavior of HCHO/ NO_2 ratio well mimic the one of O_3 during time. In particular, it is evident how on the days in which the O_3 at the ground exceeds the limit of $120 \mu g/m^3$, the HCHO/ NO_2 ratio is always above 1 and, in some case, above 2 (Fig. 2). This result is a strong indication that at SPC the O_3 production mainly takes place in NO_x -limited regime. A largely expected result considering that SPC is a rural site.

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From Fig. 1, we also observed that in spring (from March to May) HCHO/NO₂ ratio and O₃ grow with different rates. At the same time, if we look in the same period but in Fig. 5, where we used ΔO₃ instead of O₃, the growth rates seem more similar also in this season. This result possibly indicates that at least part of the O₃ increase in Spring is due to transport effects. To better understand this latest result, we investigated the backward trajectories using the NOAA HYSPLIT model [RD-6]. The frequency of trajectories for March 2022 is reported in Fig. 6. As can be seen, the transport during this month mainly comes from the North-East Italy and Europe.

Figure 6: Backward trajectory frequencies for March 2022 from HYSPLIT model.

The transport of air masses from North in this season can be a possible source of enhanced O₃ values. The correlation with temperature indicates that, the main O₃ production mainly happens for temperature above 25°C. At the same time, the correlation with the relative humidity indicates that happens for relative humidity lower than 60%.

As reported in other works, using MAX-DOAS measurements to study the HCHO/NO₂ ratio in relation to ozone production [RD-4, RD-5], our results highlight that the meteorological conditions in SPC affected the concentration levels and temporal variations of NO₂ and HCHO and O₃ production: temperature and water vapour are strictly correlated to ozone levels. No correlation with wind direction and strength has been found due to the stability of the atmosphere in the Po Valley and once again remarking the representativeness of the SPC observatory.

6. Conclusions

This study aimed to demonstrate that HCHO/NO₂ ratio from MAX-DOAS measurement in SPC can be used to study the processes related to O₃ formation and pollution at the ground.

The HCHO/NO₂ ratio correlates well with O₃ and ΔO₃ at the ground with an indication of transport of O₃ polluted air masses from North-Eastern Italy and central Europe in Spring 2022. The link between days with O₃ values over the limit of 120 μg/m³ and HCHO/NO₂ ratio indicates that, as expected, at SPC we are in presence of a NO_x limited (or sensitive) regime.

Further investigations, that are out of the scope of this project, are required to understand the entity of transport of air masses on O₃ values. In addition, removing the seasonality from the data can better evidence correlations in some specific cases.

Unfortunately, no CO measurement at the ground is available at SPC (ARPAE performs CO measurements only in the Bologna urban area), thus it is not possible to distinguish between primary and secondary sources of the O₃ production.

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